

Gallacetophenone Isonicotinoyl Hydrazone (GAPINH) as an Analytical Reagent for the Determination of Aluminium(III)

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Aluminium(III) forms an yellow coloured soluble complex with gallacetophenone isonicotinoyl hydrazone at pH 4.0. Beer's law is obeyed upto 1.90 ppm of aluminium(III) at 405 nm. The effect of pH, reagent concentration and diverse ions have been studied. The stability constant of the complex is 7.41×10^6 . The molar absorptivity and Sandell sensitivity are 1.07×10^4 lit.mole⁻¹.cm⁻¹ and 0.0025 μ g.cm⁻², respectively. The proportional decrease in the colour of the complex on gradual addition of fluoride or oxalate has been utilised for indirect determination of fluoride or oxalate in microgram quantities.

GALLACETOPHENONE isonicotinoyl hydrazone reacts with aluminium(III) to form a yellow coloured soluble complex in the pH range 2 to 8. This colour reaction is used to determine aluminium directly and fluoride and oxalate indirectly. The results are communicated herein.

Experimental

Reagents: Gallacetophenone isonicotinoyl hydrazone (GAPINH) was prepared in the laboratory and purified by recrystallisation from 50% aqueous dimethylformamide. The purity was checked by tlc.

Aluminium nitrate (0.01 M) solution was prepared from A.R. sample and standardised by oxine method¹.

Solutions of sodium fluoride and sodium oxalate in conductivity water were prepared from B.D.H., A.R. samples.

Apparatus: A Beckmann DK-2A UV-visible recording spectrophotometer, an Elico spectrophotometer, Model CL-24 and an Elico pH meter Model LI-10T were used.

Results and Discussion

Since the complex and the reagent showed maximum and negligible absorbance respectively at 405 nm, the absorbance measurements on the complex were made at this wave length. Effect of pH and concentration of the reagent showed that the absorbance is maximum at pH 4.0 and in presence of a 10 fold excess of the reagent.

Procedure:

A known aliquot of the standard metal ion solution is taken in a 10 ml measuring flask and 1.0 ml of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (pH 4.0) and 1.0 ml of the reagent ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) solution are added. The contents of the flask are made up to

mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution is measured at 405 nm against the reagent blank. The procedure is repeated with known but different aliquots.

Beer's law range, sensitivity:

A straight line passing through the origin was obtained between absorbance and the amount of aluminium in the region 0.05-1.90 μ g/ml. The optimum concentration range as per Ringbom plot² was 0.5-1.90 μ g/ml.

The molar absorptivity and Sandell³ photometric sensitivity are 1.07×10^4 litre. mole⁻¹. cm⁻¹ and 0.0025 μ g. cm⁻². ml⁻¹, respectively.

Nature and stoichiometry of the complex:

Ion exchange studies showed that the complex is cationic in nature. The composition of the complex is established as 1 : 1 by Job's continuous variation⁴, molar ratio⁵ and slope ratio methods⁶. The stability constant is found to be 7.41×10^6 .

Effect of diverse ions:

The effect of diverse ions on the determination of 1.35 μ g/ml of Al(III) was studied. Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺, chloride, bromide, iodide, bromate, sulphate, nitrate, ascorbate did not interfere even upto 3000 ppm. The tolerance limits of other ions causing deviation of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance are given in the parenthesis (ppm): Mn²⁺ (2000), Zr(IV) (450), Zn²⁺ (100), Pb²⁺ (30), Ni²⁺ (20), tartrate (15), citrate (5), EDTA (10).

Mo(VI), U(VI), V(V), Ti(IV), V(IV), Cr(VI), Fe(III), Bi(III), Cu²⁺, iodate, when present in 1 ppm, were found to interfere in the colour reaction. Fluoride and oxalate interfere in the reaction by discharging the colour of the reaction.

Determination of fluoride and oxalate:

Addition of micro amounts of fluoride or oxalate ions to the Al(III)-reagent complex resulted in a

proportional decrease of the absorbance. The bleaching effect of fluoride or oxalate has been utilised for indirect spectrophotometric determination of fluoride and oxalate in the range 2.70 ppm and 1.35 ppm, respectively.

To 1.0 ml portions of the reagent ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) solution taken in each of a set of 10 ml volumetric flasks, 1.0 ml of buffer solution (pH 4.0) and 2.5 ml of aluminium nitrate ($2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) solution were added. A known amount of fluoride (0.2 to 5.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was added to each of these flasks and the contents made up to the mark with conductivity water. The absorbance of the solutions was measured at 405 nm against reagent as blank. The absorbance data revealed a linear decrease in the absorbance with increase of fluoride upto 2.70 ppm (Fig. 2). The amount of fluoride consumed upto the inflexion point revealed a stoichiometry of 1 : 2 between aluminium and fluoride. The procedure is repeated

with oxalate. Similar results were obtained with the stoichiometry corresponding to 1 : 1. On the basis of the stoichiometry the following reactions are proposed for the bleaching action.

Most of the organic reagents employed for the photometric determination of aluminium(III) are lake forming reagents or indirect determination by dissolving the precipitates. On the other hand, the present method is simple, sensitive and rapid. The colour formation is instantaneous and remains stable for 48 hr. The method is useful in the determination of the amount of fluoride or oxalate in water and industrial waste. This was used to determine fluoride in samples of drinking water collected from bore-wells in and around Warangalcity. The results agreed very well with those obtained by standard methods.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of aluminium-GAPINH at pH 4.0.

Fig. 2. Absorbance of Al-GAPINH complex vs amount of fluoride/oxalate.

Sample No.	Source	Fluoride determined (ppm)	
		Proposed method	Standard method
1.	Bore-well inside RECOW Campus	1.65	1.70
2.	Bore-well opp. near P. H. Div. Office	1.70	1.80
3.	Bore-well opposit House No. 7-7-56	1.30	1.30
4.	Bore-well backside of Ekasila Hotel	1.80	1.80

The standard deviation and coefficient of variation at different concentration ranges are given below :

Aluminium taken	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
0.54 ppm	0.008	3.77
1.08 ppm	0.011	2.49
1.62 ppm	0.021	3.28

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